

COMPUTERS IN OCEANOGRAPHY - TRADEOFFS AND TRENDS

Lawrence J. Rosenblum and J. Dean Clamons

Naval Research Laboratory
Washington D. C. 20375

ABSTRACT

Minicomputer and microcomputer systems, designed for specific oceanographical field experiments, have become commonplace. This paper will examine both the changes to these computer systems which are occurring due to developments in the computer sciences and also the tradeoffs which must be made in system design. Emphasis will be placed on the effects of these developments on other discipline scientists who utilize computer data acquisition systems in the field.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of computer systems for the collection, storage and display of oceanographic data began to come of age during the latter part of the past decade. At the Naval Research Laboratory (NRL), for example, sophisticated minicomputer systems have been developed for members of a wide range of oceanographic disciplines including physical and chemical oceanographers, ocean engineers, geophysicists, acousticians and atmospheric physicists. These systems are now used on very nearly all oceanographic experiments, and as many as eight such systems have been placed aboard a single research vessel. Scientists who rarely or never used computer systems for data acquisition in the early and mid 1970's are now using these systems on a routine basis.

As the cost of oceanographic experimentation continues to rise, it will become ever more necessary to utilize to the fullest every data collection opportunity. Platforms which are less expensive than ships will be sought out and used; at NRL we have seen an increased use of aircraft for collection of certain types of data (ref. 1). Figure 1 shows a typical aircraft computer system installation on a P3C Orion aircraft. Less expensive craft such as barges are also being used where practical. Full utilization of these alternate platforms will rely upon the continuing trend of packing more computer capability into smaller packages for less money.

At the same time new developments such as the reduced price and size of computer memory, the advent of 32-bit minicomputers, and the use of distributed systems are creating a far greater

computational ability in shipboard computer systems. One can expect that future experiments will be designed so that the experimenter will choose how to proceed depending upon an evaluation of the processed data.

Figure 1 - Gravity/Magnetics Data Collection System on NRL Aircraft.

2. BACKGROUND

Let us examine the requirements for a typical shipboard data collection mission at NRL today. Digital data are collected from whatever navigation devices are in use during the experiment, usually the NORTHSTAR LORAN C receiver, although recently a receiver for the Global Positioning System (GPS) has also been used. Navigation data are stored in disc data files, typically at a rate of one sample per minute. Real-time navigation plots are also produced. The navigation data files also contain ships sensor data such as speed, heading, wind speed and direction. Both XBT (expendible bathythermograph) data and CTD (conductivity-temperature-depth) microprofiler data are taken. The XBT data are digitized in real-time and stored on disc files for future plotting. The CTD data are displayed graphically in real-time and stored on magnetic tape (ref. 2). The real-time CTD graphical display is often used to determine the placement of other devices in the water, although several experiments in recent years have been designed primarily for the collection of CTD data. XBT data is sampled

at a rate of between 4 and 100 samples per second; CTD data involves (depending on the model used) scanning up to 10 data bytes at rates of 32 or 50 scans per second. Figure 2 shows a system set up for the acquisition of CTD data. In addition, each researcher will have his own special equipment, ranging from magnetometers to acoustic arrays to devices for the measurement of underwater fluorescence. The digital data acquisition system must interface to these devices and acquire and store their data. This has required handling data rates of up to several thousand samples per second. The computer system is also required to perform a variety of tasks on the acquired data, ranging from making simple plots to sophisticated Fourier analysis.

Thus, the typical shipboard computer system must be capable of handling a wide variety of chores, often simultaneously. Yet the requirements of the oceanographic community do not yet approach current minicomputer system limitations.

Figure 2 - Computer System for CTD Data Acquisition.

In order to evaluate current trends it is useful to compare system capabilities today with that of five years ago. The numbers in Table 1 apply to Hewlett Packard (HP) 1000 series systems and peripherals as actually used in field experiments by NRL; however, similar numbers would apply for other minicomputer manufacturers.

The change in capability is significant. The large increase in computer memory allows many more programs to be present in memory simultaneously while supporting operating systems with greater capabilities. This memory is also accessible at higher speeds than that of five years ago. The larger disc capacity allows direct disc storage of more data while also supporting a greater data processing capability. Twice as much data can now be placed on a single magnetic tape (and higher density magnetic tape drives are commercially available should higher data rates require their use). Intelligent terminals (computer terminals

containing a programmable microprocessor), some of which contain their own cartridge tape drives, are inexpensive and are commonly used as system terminals. These intelligent terminals offer both a stand-alone capability as data collection controllers for low data rate devices (ref. 3) and a capability for acting in conjunction with the main computer system for data acquisition and display.

DEVICE	5 YEARS AGO	TODAY
Computer Memory	64K wds	256K wds
Memory Cycle Time	980 ns	350 ns
Removable Disc	1.25M wds	25.0M wds
Magnetic Tape Drive	800 BPI	1600 BPI
Intelligent Terminal	No	Yes
Programming Language	FORTRAN IV	FORTRAN 77

Table 1 - Comparison of Minicomputer Systems of Five Years Ago with Today.

3. COMPUTERIZED NAVIGATION

Accurate navigation is a requirement of all oceanographic research and survey work. The most common methods of shipboard navigation in recent years have been LORAN-C, satellite (using the Navy Transit Satellite System), and dead reckoning. Each has its disadvantages: LORAN-C has a limited area of coverage, satellite navigation is not continuous, and dead reckoning is quite inaccurate. Inertial systems are used on some ships, but they are very expensive and suffer from long term drift.

There are a variety of local navigation systems which are quite accurate although they have limited ranges and often require installation of accurately located stationary equipment. Most aircraft navigation is done by inertial systems sometimes aided by LORAN-C and OMEGA. These systems are sufficiently accurate for most work, but some recent work (ref. 1) has required better determination of platform velocity.

A few years ago the output of navigation instruments typically consisted of raw navigation data such as ranges, range differences, or changes in range. These data then required considerable processing in order to determine platform positions. The electrical characteristics of the output were widely varied, often requiring development of special hardware interfaces. The outputs are now typically RS-232C or IEEE-488 compatible making them much easier to handle. Recently the trend in navigation instruments has been toward including in the device a microprocessor which calculates current position and velocity. Though the burden on the central computer system is thereby reduced, the central computer system is still left with the task of combining the outputs of a number of navigation devices to produce an optimal estimate of position.

During the last two years NRL has been using a GPS receiver on an experimental basis on both ships and aircraft. The GPS system, presently under development, provides continuous positional accuracy of about ten meters and is applicable worldwide. Currently GPS is available for only about four hours a day, and the existing receivers are

expensive prototype models. It can be expected that future receivers will be available at prices comparable to the present cost of Transit Satellite receivers. GPS receivers will have built-in computers which will calculate the receiver's position and velocity to an accuracy which will satisfy the requirements of very nearly all oceanographic work. The oceanographic computer systems will therefore be relieved of navigation tasks except for that of logging the data.

4. TRADEOFFS

The designer of a minicomputer system for at-sea data acquisition must make many tradeoffs in defining the system (ref. 4). Since these are all to some degree dependent upon the machine available (i.e., on the manufacturer), many of these tradeoffs are computer dependent. However, certain tradeoffs can be discussed in general terms.

One area which involves many decisions is in the design of an interface between a scientific research instrument and the computer. Some factors which must be considered are: (a) the data rates required; (b) the format in which the data will be available; (c) the division of labor between software and hardware; (d) the availability of I/O (input-output) ports; and (e) the amount of time available for hardware development. The tradeoff between hardware and software is often a complicated decision. Software is generally more flexible and is easier and faster to develop, so hardware requirements are minimized wherever possible. The principal purpose of a hardware interface is to condition the data for compatibility with existing hardware and software. Using hardware to multiplex and buffer the data often speeds throughput and reduces the number of I/O channels required. The life-expectancy of the research device is also relevant since only a device which is intended for frequent use in the field would merit hardware development.

The choice of computer processor for an experiment is another tradeoff area. Here, data rates and the number of different parameters measured drive the choice between the use of a minicomputer system or microprocessors. Generally, the amount of data required will exceed microprocessor capabilities; however, where only a few parameters are desired from a single research device at low data rates the microprocessor, or alternately the intelligent terminal, becomes an attractive alternative.

Another decision lies in the choice of programming language - should real-time software be developed in assembly language or higher level languages such as FORTRAN and BASIC. On minicomputer systems languages such as FORTRAN combine with real-time operating systems to provide more than enough capability to meet the data rate requirements encountered in oceanography. While assembly language programming will sometimes offer advantages in simplicity for interfacing purposes, they have the corresponding disadvantage of being difficult to maintain and modify in the

field, especially if the computer specialist is not the program's author. The risks involved in taking software which cannot be readily understood and modified into the field make the use of assembly language highly undesirable. Even for the microprocessor case, if another language (e.g. BASIC) is available and capable of dealing with the task, it will be, for the reasons given above, the superior choice.

5. TRENDS

Many trends which were predictable a half decade ago (ref. 5) are now coming to pass. Others, such as the applicability of distributed systems to wide varieties of computer systems, are so potent that they are modifying the outlook for the future of oceanographic field computer systems.

The number of bits per word has historically defined the size of a computer system. A 64 bits system was large, 32 bits was midsized, 16 bits per word defined a minicomputer and 8 bits a microprocessor (this definition is no longer valid). The basic tradeoff here was one of system size and cost vs. computational ability. Once the experiences of the late 1960's demonstrated that standard, commercially available computers would work in the hostile shipboard environment, minicomputers were chosen for shipboard operations. This was justified in terms of both portability and cost - minicomputer systems were small enough to allow installation aboard ships and had enough capability to get the job done. In addition, the minicomputers had modest power requirements and could more easily be interfaced to other equipment. However, as data rate requirements and also computational (as opposed to data acquisition) requirements become greater, certain limitations are reached. One of these is that a 16 bit word can directly address 2^{16} words of memory. Minicomputer manufacturers are, to some extent, overcoming this restriction by extended memory addressing schemes including bank switching and virtual memory addressing. However, while these methods offer a significant improvement in the capability of minicomputers, they slow memory access enough to cause problems in real-time or even certain computational applications.

Both computer memory and external storage devices such as discs are becoming remarkably inexpensive, and all indications are that memory, on a per word basis, will continue to decrease in cost. Highly reliable, high density, fixed-medium disc units, which contain their own magnetic tape backup, are available for minicomputer systems today. These units currently have a capacity of several hundred megabytes. Thus the future will offer a vast capability to store and process large quantities of collected data on minicomputer systems without resorting to the use of magnetic tape. This will permit very complicated real-time processing in the field to be performed.

Concurrently, the advances in very large scale integration (VLSI) are reducing the cost and increasing the speed of the processing section of computers. As a result, most minicomputer manu-

facturers have introduced 32 bit minicomputers (the so-called super-minis) and it can be anticipated that within a few years all minicomputers will be 32 bits per word machines with a capability well beyond those of the mid-sized computers of a few years back. At the same time microcomputers will become 16 bit machines instead of 8 bits, will add more capability to support peripherals, and, in short, will begin to look more like current minicomputers.

Significant advances are being made in software as well as hardware. The increased computer memory size is enabling minicomputer manufacturers to provide system software with increased capability. One important improvement has been in the area of system generation. In the past, even very small system changes, for example replacing a line printer with another line printer requiring a different driver, would require a full system regeneration. Even if all goes well a system generation requires the better part of a day. Today, many changes to the system can be performed by a system reconfiguration process requiring only a few minutes. These changes include driver replacement, equipment table reconfiguration, and changes to system memory partition definitions. These software improvements free the computer specialist to spend time on the specific problems of the research scientist.

The effect of all this upon the research scientist will be the availability of a wider range of shipboard systems than has been the case. At the top end, for prices comparable to today's minicomputer systems, 32 bit machines will acquire and display data at higher data rates than at present and will also provide a very significant shipboard capability for processing the data. On the other hand, very inexpensive microcomputer systems will have sufficient capability to perform many tasks.

Interfacing to oceanographic equipment has recently been simplified by greater standardization. The makers of scientific instruments for oceanography are showing concern for computer interfacing as part of their product design. In particular, many instruments are now offering the use of the IEEE-488 (GPIB) bus for computer interfacing. This interfacing method is particularly useful for field work because, since GPIB devices can be daisy-chained together, at least 15 GPIB devices can be interfaced using only one computer I/O slot. In addition, GPIB generally provides a capability to buffer data, which often simplifies interfacing.

Another very useful design trend in oceanographic instrumentation has been the introduction of microprocessors within the measurement device for use in I/O. These microprocessors are very useful for the instrument user; they can be used to format data, message data, buffer data, etc. As this type of design becomes used on more instruments, the scientist will find that he has a new and very useful capability to manipulate data at the instrument, not only simplifying computer interfacing but also facilitating simple data storage and display.

The Neil Brown/W.H.O.I. CTD microprofiler,

which is an instrument that makes fine-scale measurements of conductivity, temperature and pressure (ref. 6), illustrates many of the above points. This device was first used at NRL in 1977 and has been used on virtually every shipboard experiment since. The CTD of 1977 sampled at 32 frames of data per second and offered both serial and parallel data ports on the CTD deck unit. However in order to handle software timing problems, a hardware interface was built to sample and hold a full data frame. This hardware interface provided the software with sufficient time to perform all storage and display functions while simultaneously acquiring the next data buffer. More recently an IEEE-488 bus interface was made available on the CTD deck unit. This improvement removed the need for a hardware interface between the deck unit and the computer and also freed additional computer I/O slots since the CTD could now join the other GPIB equipment and share a single slot.

The ability of on-board computer systems to handle larger quantities of data at higher speeds has encouraged scientists to investigate many smaller scale phenomena than has previously been possible. Of course, this research is made possible by parallel advances in sensor technology which provides the required data. The CTD serves as an example; the manufacturer is now offering a 100 frame per second model.

Experience has dictated that, as researchers become familiarized with computer data acquisition, a demand arises for higher data rates. This has generally been true even where the need for higher data rates was not foreseen. The oceanographic researcher can expect that manufacturers will provide oceanographic equipment which will operate at higher data rates than those of today. Computer systems themselves will also come in smaller packages and lend themselves more readily to installation in cramped quarters such as are encountered on aircraft.

Distributed system refers to the capability of linking several computers together to form a network of computers. These computers can then share resources, i.e., one computer can send data from its disc pack through the distributed system to a second computer which can then process the data and plot them on a plotting device which is physically attached to a third. The advantages of putting several computers into a distributed network are obvious and this concept is being applied throughout the work of computers. For field experiments in oceanography it means obtaining greater processing power from the same equipment. One computer system can now process data while a second system collects the data without any requirement for manually moving the data from one system to the other. Indeed, the second system need not even necessarily have the capability of storing the data! Another advantage of distributed systems is that one system can easily be designed to take over the chores of another, so that system difficulties due to hardware failure can be more easily and rapidly corrected.

Another area for discussion is the potential for transferring data from ship to the home labora-

tory by satellite. The technology for performing such a computer-to-computer transfer through commercial satellite systems (e.g. MARISAT) exists today. The limitation of this approach for data processing has been the high cost of transmitting data in this manner. However, if the cost of satellite communication were to decrease, it is easy to envision certain benefits of this approach to the researcher. Data would be transmitted to the laboratory for processing and the results returned by satellite. The need to place highly trained scientists aboard ship for the purpose of data processing would be eliminated for some applications and shipboard equipment would be reduced with a corresponding reduced potential for hardware failure.

Many other technology changes will also impact on the usage of computer systems. Fiber optic technology can be expected to provide high bandwidth, low noise data transmission paths, which will allow sensors located throughout the oceanographic platform to be connected to the computer system. The use of fiber optics will eliminate much of the noise pick up and ground loop problems which presently plague oceanographic instrumentation and will increase the speed of inter-computer communication. This increased speed will combine with the developing technology of parallel and distributed computing software to create powerful, fast and redundant local networks of computers. Advances in LSI and VLSI integrated circuit technology can produce powerful computer systems which will be collections of special purpose processors (e.g., array processors, graphics processors, and intelligent interfaces) with a central computer whose task will be to control the operation of the special purpose processors and to direct the flow of data among them.

6. CONCLUSION

During the last decade the use of oceanographic computer systems in the field has greatly enhanced the quality and quantity of the data gathered, opened up new areas of research and provided real-time information to the scientist. As the cost of taking ships to sea continues to increase, it becomes even more important to fully utilize all data collection opportunities. During the 1980's data rates and shipboard data processing requirements will increase substantially; however, the use of 32 bit minicomputers in a distributed network along with peripheral storage devices capable of holding very large amounts of data will more than meet these requirements. Interfacing oceanographic equipment to the computer will become easier as manufacturer interfaces become more standardized and intelligently designed. The shipboard system will not only collect and display data, but its data processing capabilities will be integrated into experiments to allow mid-stream modification of experiments depending upon the processed data.

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